

SOCIOLOGICAL SURVEY IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Annotation.

In the article, the author examines the features of the quality management system in the management mechanism of higher education institutions; the relationship between the expected results of its implementation and implementation, as well as conducted a sociological study and presented the results of the analysis in order to study the attitude of the faculty and staff of the university to this management resource.

Keywords.

quality, management, system, higher education institution, teachers, management, survey, respondent, assessment, consumer.

Introduction. The development of an increasing system of integrative processes and information to an international level in the context of globalization, the sharp change in the attitude towards social management of increased competition towards useful increases social adaptation in the management system. The perfection of social process management requires the improvement of the collection system by reproducing and analyzing the information of the educational system in the current conditions.

Main part. The quality management system is an administrative-managerial tool consisting in the formalization of actions by developing standards designed to coordinate the interaction of employees and controlling their implementation in order to ensure the compliance of the parameters of the activities of higher educational institutions with the established requirements. So, education as a field of Educational Services is the main, targeted component of any university, they provide educational services. In this regard, it is the most important criterion for assessing the educational activities of a foreigner.

According to economists-scientists, in the conditions of a market economy, the

need to introduce an effective system of organization management, which ensures a constant improvement of the production process, the implementation of measures to increase the competitiveness of both the product and the entire organization, is becoming increasingly important. The modern “management system should not only be able to respond to a changing situation and correct the miscalculations allowed, but also increase the pace of development of the Company” [1].

Based on the analysis of the formation and development of the quality management system, we will be able to determine some laws. Let's consider the quality management system at the micro and macrosociological level. The microsociological level is the implementation of a quality system in one separately obtained enterprise. T.V. Grekhova in his dissertation work on sociology, grekhova noted: “modern organizations are constantly looking for ways to develop themselves in order to be successful and life-resistant, and at present, one of the most universal methods of organizational development is the quality management system. A well - structured and efficiently functioning quality management system in an organization is a powerful tool for improving the overall efficiency of a business organization and, as a result, improving the quality of goods and services, reducing the cost of manufactured products and reducing the cost. Therefore, the creation and constant improvement of the quality management system is one of the most important competitive advantages that lead the company to success, and strengthening its position in the market allows the organization to increase the well-being of its employees, ensure social guarantees, and ultimately increase their confidence in the future through this” [2].

Research methodology. The need for management is related to the dynamics of the managed system. As the management theory literature states, if any system can always be in the same state, then there is no need for management. The meaning of management is to influence the dynamic system in order to make certain changes. The problems of reflexive management are covered in the works of T.M.Davidenko, B.C.Lazarev, M.M.Potashnik, P.I.Tretyakov, T.N.Shamova [3].

The process of reflexive management of education, in particular, the educational institution, and is associated with factors affecting the development of the individual, in which the meaning of actions is realized, the need for targeted transformational activity is realized. Deep self-awareness leads to the development of the following processes: “self - awareness - self-expression - self-affirmation - self-expression - self-control”. In the process of managing the development of an educational institution, analysis and diagnostics are important in the organization of consulting activities, on the basis of which a consulting process or a project for the development of an

educational institution is planned and organized. In this, reflexive management is based on self-analysis, self-assessment. Professors will have to accurately assess the results of their activities by external experts on indicators that analyze the activities of the institution [4,5].

In recent years, the most important trend in the development of educational quality management, which determines the essence of educational quality management, is a systematic approach, which is considered not only a type of methodological research, but also a modern method of management thinking that allows providing holistic and integrated educational management in a complex dynamic environment.

Analysis and results. Any management system should not only take into account the official indicators and activity results, but should turn to the analysis of its real content. When it comes to quality management in higher educational institutions, it is clear that an objective assessment of quality and overall management efficiency cannot be obtained only on the basis of the results of checking the necessary documents, the existence of a set of relevant educational and methodological documents, etc., and a comprehensive approach to determining quality criteria is necessary.

Our pilot study showed that there are serious difficulties for the introduction and implementation of the quality management system in the management system of higher educational institutions. Summarizing the results of the research, it can be noted that several factors can hinder the creation of a quality management system in higher education. The purpose of our research was to clarify the evaluation of the content and effectiveness of the quality management system in the university by professors and teachers, as well as their attitude to this management resource and the prospects of its implementation in higher education institutions.

One of our tasks is to obtain information from professors and teachers on the evaluation of the effectiveness of the quality management system at the university, taking into account the experience and traditions of foreign higher education, from the point of view of local peculiarities, to determine the prospects for the quality management system and its implementation in higher educational institutions.

The research was conducted in the higher educational institutions of our republic in March-October 2022. 612 respondents from higher educational institutions took part in the research. The survey questionnaire consisted of 25 questions, mainly about the university and social, economic and other conditions, i.e. the attitude of professors and teachers to the teaching process, the quality of education at the university, the level of satisfaction with the educational process,

and the problems of evaluating the quality management system and its effectiveness.

Among the respondents, 74% of professors and associate professors who have been working at the university for more than 15 years, 26% of teachers and senior teachers with 5 years or more of work experience participated. The age of the respondents was as follows: young teachers (up to 35 years old) - 46.5%, "mature" teachers over 35 years old - 53.5%. Males and females accounted for 38% and 62%, respectively.

When faculty and staff were asked about the quality management system, it was found that 45% of them had knowledge and the remaining 55% had partial knowledge. In order for professors to be able to fully assess the need for a new management resource, it is necessary to introduce them to the experience in this field, explain the essence and show what needs to be done to make this resource work effectively. Most theorists emphasize that the process of introducing a quality management system in an organization should begin with training. Rejection of innovations is often associated with a misunderstanding of their nature and purpose. At the initial stage of introducing the quality management system to educational institutions, the process of teaching its essence is often carried out on a mandatory basis. A compelling factor can lead to rejection of the idea itself.

Summarizing the results of the survey, it was shown that the professors, staff, who have knowledge of the quality management system, in general, positively evaluated the achievements of the quality management system and formed very clear and interesting answers, because the respondents also had the opportunity to answer open-ended questions.

One of the main questions of the survey is "What do you think "customer satisfaction" means in the quality management system at the university?" is called, 41% of respondents "consumers will have highly qualified specialists", 35% of respondents "as students, parents, employers, and the state, consumers have no objection to the quality of higher education", 22% of respondents "this is a term taken from the field of economics, it cannot be related to education", and 2% of the respondents did not answer. The consumer today represents a unique invisible force for the university that can significantly influence its destiny. In fact, the consumer in the quality management system for the field of higher education is understood as the employer, the state and society as a whole, as well as the student and his parents. Answering the question, 22% of the respondents definitely disagreed with the idea that the term "consumer" should be used in higher education. After all, when it comes to education, training, worldview formation, it

is difficult to connect these processes with the concept of "consumer". In our opinion, this is due to the interpretation of education as a service in modern conditions. However, we noted above that such an interpretation should be supplemented with meaningful features.

Respondents were asked, "In your opinion, what factors can have a negative impact on the implementation of the quality management system at the university?" we asked the question and received the following answers: "there is no methodology adapted to the higher education system for the introduction of the quality management system at the university" - 41%, "the lack of knowledge of the management and employees of the university in the field of the quality management system" - 38%, "the introduction of the quality management system of the university not ready" - 56%, "lack of organic communication between the university management and employees" - 28%, "I have trouble answering" - 5%, "other factors" - 2%. In answering this question, experts were not limited in choosing any factor. Analyzing the obtained data, we can conclude that all the above factors can affect the implementation of the quality management system at the university to one degree or another. There are, of course, certain difficulties in the direct application of quality management system standards in universities. The system of quality management system standards developed for manufacturing enterprises is not adapted to the specific characteristics of the relevant field of education and is not very developed. We also emphasize that when talking about education, it is necessary to understand the nature and purpose of this social phenomenon. Its result is not a technical product or an inanimate object, but an intellectually prepared culturally and spiritually formed person.

Respondents were asked "Does the introduction of the quality management system at the university affect the improvement of the quality of education?" when we asked the question, 10% of them "definitely have an impact", 31% "have an impact, because the quality management system is aimed at meeting the needs of consumers", 39% "have only a partial impact, because the quality of education does not depend only on how effective the management is at the university ", 12% marked "no effect, because formalization and documentation of all processes cannot improve the quality of education", 7% marked "no effect at all", and the rest were difficult to answer.

The quality of education is perceived differently by everyone. Some believe that the main quality of education is the satisfaction of consumer needs, while others see it as the presence of developed professional and general cultural competences. In this article, we presented data from sociological surveys conducted

to determine the attitude of the population to the quality of education. Our survey confirmed the versatility and multi-value of this concept. This was also reflected in the respondents' answers to the given question.

Conclusions and suggestions. Higher education is one of the most important factors of economic, spiritual and social development of society, because it is necessary to rely on the scientific and intellectual potential of our country to accelerate economic and social growth. This, in turn, should serve as a condition for the development of innovative economy and social development of society [6].

To achieve success in the modern world, to enter the global educational space, higher education institutions must solve the issue of using new management technologies. This allows them to be competitive, to improve the culture and efficiency of their work, which serves the further development and well-being of the university.

Today, there are different approaches to managing universities. Effective management tools include the quality management system, which can serve as an effective element of innovative management of the university, taking into account the specific characteristics of the educational sector, as well as the existing traditions and experience of the higher educational institution.

By taking into account and supplementing the opinions of a number of quality management system researchers, the concept of quality management system through the methodology of active activity can be defined as follows: it is from the formalization of actions by developing standards designed to coordinate the interaction of employees to ensure the compliance of university activity parameters with established requirements and monitoring their implementation. is a management tool.

The analysis of the conducted research made it possible to formulate the following fundamental principles necessary for quality management in higher educational institutions:

1. Quality management should be multi-level and its main component should be education and development of students. This principle includes the use of various methods (tests, questionnaires, etc.) to determine the quality of education.
2. Quality management programs should include research and analysis of results. The results must be interpreted, analyzed and stored. Therefore, quality management is useful in the future, when comparing results that differ over time.
3. Quality management programs must be realistic. It is clear that quality management must start with realistic expectations in terms of achieving the intended goals.

4. The goals of higher educational institutions should correspond to its resources.

5. The main advantage of quality management results is that it provides information that is not available in any other way, but is necessary for decision making.

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